

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	
GPR	11	B		Min: 61.936 Max: 62.773	1391 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 1828-52 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: *Western Wall Room No 6* Covered by SU: 1327 Fills SU: Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction FORMATION PROCESS: Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX				
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive <table border="1"> <tr> <th>Compaction</th> <th>Color</th> </tr> <tr> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft </td> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) </td> </tr> </table>	Compaction	Color	<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
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UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to: Is bound to (only for masonry): 1309

Is abutted by: Abuts: 1400, 1405, 1425, 1414

Is covered by: *SU 1327, 0* Covers:

Is cut by: Cuts:

Is filled by: Fills:

OBSERVATIONS: *Hot + dry conditions, excavated w/ pickaxe + trowel.*

DESCRIPTION

Position within sector: *South-western corner of area B, room #6, western wall of the room.*

Shape: *Rectangular wall.*

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:

Cut edges: rounded straight

Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping

Cut bottom: flat concave irregular

How is cut top edge? sharp rounded

How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded

Observations:

Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment: a mostly straight wall heading southwest, parallel to the "via claudia" and perpendicular to 1304

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size: Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)
 Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)
 Wall finishing: Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains: 550 cent x 18 x 25 (80 or 100 part)

Description: The blocks for wall follows the gradual slope of the hill southwest, beginning at the threshold of the house and extending down to the excavation limit. Most of the excavated wall is one stone deep, but the area directly south of 1304 is one stone higher. The stone on the northern end (near the threshold) is slightly thinner.

INTERPRETATION Built concurrently with the street, the eastern end of which it encloses. The long slender stone abutting the threshold is more in line with the construction of the house than the road relative to the rest of the wall. Part of the wall, the block that is higher with a square cut and corner missing, is likely reused. The presence of a section (perhaps the size of one stone) with two blocks as well as the identical ashlar in addition to with the other differences in construction might indicate later repairs and reuse.

Appendix to description: The stone that is higher than the rest has a square on its southern-facing end, and it is missing about 9 centimeters from the top for the final 18 centimeters extending south (see drawing). One section, third to the south, is two stones, one of into the other of ashlar. The two southernmost stones are identically sized ashlar.

SOIL SAMPLING: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	NON SOIL SAMPLES: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	SIEVING: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Total volume of layer (buckets):	If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):	Total volume of layer (buckets):
Sample quantity (buckets):		Sample quantity (buckets):
Sample fraction (%):		Sample fraction (%):
	Size:	

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Poor	Filled-out by	AB + AKR + ALG	on 15/7/2011
	Revised by	CHH	on 21/7/2011
	PDFd by	ECR	on 1/8/2011
	Entered by		on